

SOP DNA extraction from microplastics in water samples

1. Introduction and Scope

The main purpose of this SOP is to describe the analysis of microbial communities attached to microplastics recovered from water samples of selected locations of the Red River Delta and Cat Ba Island, Viet Nam.

2. Principle of the Method

As previously described in the SOP “Water column collection, filtration, and sample storage for microbiological analyses of microplastics”, sequential filtration will be used to separate and collect MPs and free-living microorganisms from water samples. 100 L – 400L of water will be sampled from each listed location and depth, each resulting in a concentrate of approx. 50 mL. Nylon filters (NF, pore size 45 µm) will be used to collect MPs over 45 µm in size, while membrane filters (MCE, pore size 0.22 µm) will be used to retain free-living bacteria from the water samples.

3. Chemicals and Reagents

- 70% EtOH (alcohol) for sterilisation of equipment.
- 0.2 M Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS)
- DNA extraction kit
- Qubit reagents
- Minlon reagents

4. Materials and Equipment

- Cellulose nitrate membrane filters (0.22 µm pore size, ϕ 47 mm)
- Nylon filters (45 µm pore size, ϕ 47 mm)
- Flat tip tweezers
- Gloves
- Falcon tubes (50 mL) for concentrate storage
- Falcon tubes (15 mL) for filter storage
- Eppendorf tubes (5 mL)
- Microcentrifuge tubes (0.5 mL)
- Cooler with dry ice on board / fridge
- Freezer on facilities near sampling sites
- Vacuum filtration equipment (glass funnels, HDPE tubing, and pump)
- Stainless steel spatula / spoon
- Micro centrifuge
- Qubit fluorometer
- Minlon Flow cell

5. Method for water collection and filtration

5.1 Water collection

5.1.1 Water (100 L – 400 L) from each location and depth are sampled for MPs by the pump method at the following locations:

5.2 Refer to the [MicrobiologyUK-MolecularBiologyFieldSamples_Nov22](#) for and updated version of samples names and locations.

5.1.2 Immediately upon retrieval, the resulting concentrate (water and debris, including MPs), thereafter “samples”, will be transferred onto a 50 mL Falcon tube, and placed in a fridge at 2 C until further processing on board of the boat or on land.

5.2 Water filtration

5.2.1 Following antiseptic techniques (gloves, surfaces sprayed with 70% ethanol (EtOH) and wiped with a lint-free 100% cotton cloth, water samples will be split onto two fractions (a, b of 25 mL each) for subsequent DNA extraction from MPs and imaging analysis.

5.2.2 Before sample filtration, flat tweezers and vacuum filtration device will be wiped with 70% EtOH. Distilled water will be passed through before every experimental session.

5.2.3 Nylon net filters (pore size 45 um) will be placed onto the filtration device, using flat tweezers, to collect microparticles on the sample.

5.2.4 The resulting filter, holding MPs, will be placed into an empty Falcon tube and immediately stored at – 80 C or into the DNA extraction kit lysis buffer for subsequent DNA extraction.

5.2.5 Tubes will be labelled with location and depth of water filtered using a permanent waterproof tape. Separate tubes will be used for each filter.

5.3 DNA extraction

5.3.1 Depending on the extraction kit: A) insert the filter paper into a 5 mL bead tube; or B) if using a Ribolyser instrument for lysis, using a sterile forceps the filter will be transferred into sterile Petri dish. The filter will then be broken into 4 pieces with the pair of sterile forceps. Finally, using the sterile forceps, the pieces of filter will be transferred into 4 individual lysing tubes provided by the extraction kit.

5.3.2 The protocol provided by the extraction kit will be followed.

5.3.3 DNA extracts will be stored at – 80 C until further amplification, purification, and sequencing using the Oxford Nanopore Minlon sequencing platform.

5.4 DNA quantification with Qubit

5.4.1 Prepare the Qubit dsDNA BR assay standards (2) and set up the required number of microcentrifuge tubes (0.5 mL) according to the number of DNA extracts to quantify. The top of the tubes will be labelled, making sure that the walls of the tube are clean for the fluorometric readings to work appropriately.

5.4.2 The protocol by the manufacturer will be followed. Briefly, Qubit working solution (180 - 199 uL) will be added to each tube so that the final volume in each tube is 200 uL.

5.4.3 Individual DNA extracts will be added to the corresponding tube with Qubit solution. Tubes will be incubated for 2 minutes, after which the standards and samples will be read.

5.5 DNA amplification

5.5.1 Bacterial DNA will be amplified by PCR using universal bacterial primers (include barcodes to be used).

5.5.2 A PCR ready mix will be used, otherwise a master mix will be prepared with taq

polymerase, forward and reverse primers, base molecular grade water, buffer, dNTPs, magnesium chloride.

- 5.5.3 Individual DNA extracts (1 uL) will be placed in tubes containing 50 uL of the master mix to be amplified.
- 5.5.4 Tubes will be placed in a thermocycler and the appropriate cycle selected.
- 5.5.5 Once the cycle is over, amplicons will be either stored at – 20 C or run in an agarose gel to verify the appropriate amplicon bp size was obtained.

5.6 DNA sequencing using the Oxford Nanopore Minlon sequencing platform.

- 5.6.1 Ribosomal RNA operons will be sequenced using the SQK-16S024 16s barcoding kit on Minlon Mk 1 R9 Version flow cells.

5.7 Bioinformatic analysis

- 5.7.1 Fast5 files will be base called using the Guppy software (3.2.2), sized between 3700 and 5700 bp in length, separated by barcode, and then screened by Discontinuous Megablast against the EZ BioCloud 16S rRNA gene database using Geneious (11.1.5).23.
- 5.7.2 Best BLAST hits (BBH) will be exported as csv files and organized using pivot tables in Excel.
- 5.7.3 Further community analysis will be done using Mothur, Primer7 and the R-package Vegan.
- 5.7.4 MinION sequence reads will be made available in NCBI.

6 Documentation

Clear labelling of the tubes will be required. The labels need to include location, depth, and date of collection.

7 Safety

[Risk Assessment.](#)

8 References

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